

The Significance of Teacher Emotional Intelligence in Crucial Relationship Quality with Students: A Mixed Methods Study

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Abstract:

Globalization and crucial relationship quality with students have changed many new challenges for teachers in the world and across the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, predominantly in the higher education sector. This research paper investigates the significance of emotional intelligence in critical relationship quality with students. Several studies have examined the interaction between teacher emotional intelligence and relationship quality with students. The significance of the present study is that there has not been an experimental study that has investigated how these two variables cooperate together. Additionally, since emotion has emerged as a significant component of both teaching and learning, the potential for emotional intelligence to assess and impact the capacity of teachers to influence student achievement is vital. The aims of this study are defined as the following: first, to explore the relationship between teacher emotional intelligence, teacher-student relationship quality, and student engagement; second, to identify a statistically important relationship between teacher emotional intelligence and teacher-student relationship quality; third, to observe the important relationship between teacher emotional intelligence and student learning outcomes. The study involved a mixed-method approach and was conducted in two stages: first, the researcher gathered qualitative data by conducting individual interviews. Second, the researcher collected quantitative data by managing a questionnaire for students. Furthermore, to investigate this matter, an experimental study was conducted with the participation of 65 students from 2 universities in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq. 21 teachers were interviewed from 2 universities¹ in the same region. The findings revealed some implications with regard to the significance of teacher emotional intelligence in relationship quality with students. Firstly, teacher emotional intelligence was shown to have an eminent significance in impacting the belief with regard to student achievement in learning. Secondly, teacher emotional intelligence was shown to significantly affect student emotional, behavioural and cognitive engagement.

Key word: Emotion, Intelligence, Teacher-student relationship, Approaches, Implication

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I. Introduction

Nowadays, arguably every teacher is different; each has their backgrounds and the culture that make them unique. Over the past 20 years, according to Mehta (2015), pointed out, “the educational landscape has been dominated by an emphasis on reform efforts focused on standards-based curriculum and standardized achievement measurement” (p.67). Thus, this movement represents a seismic shift from education being conceptualized as a social process for students to a curriculum- driven, assessment-focused process. Accordingly, the shift to a curriculum and assessment-driven process is antithetical to the philosophical position of progressive education reformers of the early 20th century such as John Dewey. As stated by Dewey (1926) that educators remain focused on teaching and learning as a social experience. This research paper has split into three main parts; the **first** focuses on; the significance of teacher emotional intelligence and strategies used by Kurdish teachers in the Iraqi Kurdistan Region.

The paradigm move to standardized assessment measures has little regard for the human, teacher emotional aspects of the learning process as identified by Dewey. According to (Nation’s Report Card, 2017), school leaders have chosen to reform the public education system through a focus on the observable measures of student progress. The researchers have instantaneously been focusing on the attitudes and social interactions of the students exploring the ways that teach emotional intelligence and cognition are linked. (Garcia & Martinez

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2015). Teacher emotional intelligence has been defined as pedagogy and knowledge of content are with little regard for teacher emotional capacity. (Mortiboys, p.35, 2012). Thus, by ignoring the significance of the emotional, interpersonal experiences between teachers and students, standardized testing measures fall short of representing the entire educational experience for students. On the word of (Vygotsky & Cole, 1978), “the foundational aspects of the teaching and learning process must involve teacher and student attitudes and the motivation to teach and to learn” (p.65).

In the **second** part, the researcher believes that there is no single paradigm that could satisfactorily deal with all of the required methodological aspects. Since, the learning environment is a dynamic interaction between students and teachers, the emotional and social aspects of the learning process must be included as components of student progress. Investigating the emotional aspects of the learning process and their related components must extend beyond primary quantitative measures, instead, a qualitative investigation will be provided with a deeper understanding of the role of the human experience in teaching and learning. This allows the researcher to accomplish an understanding of the research problem and the importance of the study in the field of educational sectors. The reasons that a researcher has used mixed methods to evaluate the value of objective and subjective knowledge. In the **three**-part, the researcher briefly discussed the findings and his own experiences. It will be achieved by focusing on self-reflection and to answer the following main research questions:

1. What are the challenges of the teacher emotional intelligence related to student achievement?
2. What are the most significant impacts on teachers to use emotional intelligence to establish interpersonal relationships with students?
3. To what extent does emotional intelligence impact student engagement?

II. Research Objectives

The objectives of study are to investigate the impact of the most significant keystone in teacher emotional intelligence that makes them an effective teacher in relationship with students and to explore the relationship between emotional intelligence and teacher’s performance. Lastly, to identify most of the difficulties that are facing teachers to grasp the crucial relationship quality.

III. Part One

This part has three aims: 1) An understanding of the concept of the significance of teacher emotional intelligence. 2) A discussion on the significance of the study and the statement of the problem. 3) A good evaluation of the review of the literature.

IV. The Concept of the Teacher Emotional Intelligence

Motivation can be defined to be “the reason that guides behaviour” (Guay et al., 2010, p.712). According to the PMBOK, (2009), motivation is “powering people to achieve high levels of performance and overcoming barriers to change psychologists have provided different definitions according to attitude to the motivation phenomenon (p.73).

V. The Intelligence of the Study

The importance of the study is to state and the national curriculum standards in Kurdistan Region Iraq and emphasizing students’ achievement on standardized tests. Additionally, the current educational reform efforts have revolved from the soft skills of education to a focus on the measurable outcomes of learning. The difficulty in quantifying the emotional aspects of the learning process has remained chiefly ignored.

How teachers relate to and build positive interpersonal relationships with students is not easily quantifiable. Thus, reformers have been led to focus on other methods for school improvement that can be measured and simulated. The advancement of emotional intelligence (EI) theory has essentially allowed for the measurement of one’s emotional dimension (Mayer, 2016, p.55). Primarily, the term EI was applied to business research in examining the abilities of leaders to relate to employees. EI has expanded to other fields, including education-specific, where it has most often been used to explore the competencies of school leaders. As the development of EI tests has expanded, the data have allowed for the quantification of one’s ability to understand and interpret emotion. Hence, the exploration of teacher EI and its impact on student engagement and achievement is both timely and significant.

VI. Statement of The Problem

Hence, the exploration of teacher EI and its impact on student engagement and achievement is both timely and significant. The problem of this study is the extent to which teachers’ emotional intelligence (EI) and

interpersonal relationship quality impact student achievement and engagement; this aspect of the learning/teaching process is largely unknown. Instead, the educational theory is rich with beliefs that emotion and interpersonal relationships between teachers and students are significant to student engagement and achievement in school (Noam, 2013, p.43). However, despite the theoretical base supporting connections between emotions, relationships, and student engagement and achievement, empirical evidence is lacking. This study seeks to explore the role of teacher EI and its impact on the teaching/learning process in high school settings. As identified by Murray, Kosty, and Hauser-McLean (2016, p.22), there is little existing research on the EI of high school teachers and its impact on student learning (Murray et al., 2016, p.63). While progress has been made in exploring the emotional capacity of teachers to form quality relationships with students and the resulting influence that such relationships have on students' learning, questions remain as to how teachers best build these bonds and what their impact on student success is (Bernstein & Noam, 2013, p.78). This study will examine how the EI of high school teachers impacts student achievement, engagement, and the quality of the teacher-student interpersonal relationship.

VII. Purpose of The Study

As researchers and educators become aware of the significance of the social and emotional aspects of the teaching/ learning process, more attention is being paid to the positive interpersonal relationships that teachers maintain with students and their impact on student achievement. One theory that has been used to explain the ability of individuals to regulate and interpret their own emotions and those of others is emotional intelligence (EI) (Salovey & Mayer, 1990, p.29). EI is defined as "the ability to reason validly with emotions and with emotional related information and to use emotions to enhance thought" (Mayer, & Salovey, 2016, p.195). Emotional intelligence, a relatively new term, stands as a sound theory for interpreting the ability of teachers to form positive interpersonal relationships with students and impact school engagement and achievement. Recent research notes that the EI of teachers is a significant factor in determining the quality of interpersonal relationships they have with students (Naqvi, & Akhtar, 2016, p.25).

VIII. Relationship Quality

The terms of relationship quality and quality relationship are not interchangeable. The relationship quality encompasses two components from the perspective of the student: 1) level of support from the teacher and 2) level of conflict with the teacher (Hughes, 2012, p.88).

IX. Definitions of Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is a term that has been defined in many different ways. Thus, these various definitions are rooted in the conceptual framework of the authors who present them. The definition proposed by Mayer and Salovey (2001, p.82) will be used in this study: emotional intelligence involves the ability to perceive accurately, appraise, and express emotion; the ability to access and/ or generate feelings when they facilitate thought; the ability to understand emotion and emotional knowledge; and the ability to regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth (p.10).

X. Limitations of The Study

The primary limitation of this study will be the examination of teacher and student emotion, relationships, achievement, and engagement solely from the teachers' perspectives. Due to the inherent difficulty in using a vulnerable student population, the study will attempt to explore teacher-student interpersonal relationships as well as student achievement and engagement without assessing the students' perspectives. The few explorations into teacher-student relationship quality that have used student perspectives have demonstrated that teacher and student perceptions of the same relationship are often disparate. This incongruence may lead teachers to report levels of relationship quality with their students that are not reciprocated by students. Furthermore, if it is relying on teacher observations of student engagement and achievement may provide an incomplete perspective of how students feel, behave, and learn. Ideally, the study would include data generated from both teachers and students. However, this investigation will be confined to the perspective of teachers only, and this is a known limitation of the investigation.

XI. Teacher Emotional Intelligence

Prior evidence provided in this section has demonstrated that teaching and learning are emotional endeavours. The ability of teachers to influence the engagement of students through quality, interpersonal relationship is significant. As educational researchers continue to point to the signs of emotion in learning and, specifically, to the interpersonal relationship that exists between teachers and students, it seems that the construct of emotion in learning and, specifically, to the interpersonal relationship that exists between teachers and students, it seems that the construct of emotional intelligence is relevant to the work that teachers do. As

Raz and Zysberg (2014) noted, teaching is a profession with high levels of emotional labour. Nevertheless, despite the emotional labour of teaching, few studies have focused on the experiences of teachers (George, 2000, p.14). However, despite the emotional labour of teaching, few studies have focused on the emotional experiences of teachers (George, 2000, p.24). Teachers maintain a central role in developing and maintaining quality interpersonal relationships with students, their own EI is a significant factor in the relationships that they have with students. Although few studies have focused on the emotional experiences of teachers, EI research continues to expand from its origins in the study of education and sparingly to help interpret the experiences of educators.

XII. Student Engagement Intelligence

Student engagement is currently viewed as a meta-construct consisting of behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement (Fredricks, 2004, p.25) were the first to propose this meta-construct, recognizing that engagement within the literature often used separate and unique descriptions of the concept. A criticism of this meta construct is that in creating such a broad definition, it may describe the entire student experience, and in being so encompassing, describe nothing at all (Fredricks, 2016, p.29). Student engagement is one of the strongest predictors of academic success (Scarlett, 2015, p.87). The relationship of engagement to academic success makes it a point of interest for both researchers and educators. Teachers have been found to have a significant influence on all three forms of student engagement (Mori, &Chow, 2012, p.39). According to Harris (2011) pointed out that the potential influence of teachers on student engagement is significant due to its malleability (p.90). This influence has the potential to be either positive or negative.

XIII. Nature Of Interpersonal Relationships

In the literature, the complexity of the teacher-student relationship has most recently been understood through dynamic systems theory (Sabol, & Pinata 2012, p.44). In fact, through this lens, students are part of complex systems that include proximal and distal influences. The relationship between teacher and student is described as a proximal relationship in which both parties and their experiences influence one another. However, teachers can influence the quality of their interpersonal relationships directly and, in turn, mediate the emotional engagement levels of their student. This ability to directly influence student emotional engagement through interpersonal relationship quality gives the teacher the ability to then influence students' behavioural and cognitive engagement as well as their academic achievement (Mayer, 2016, p.66).

Establishing interpersonal relationships with teachers are the key component in establishing either high or low-quality relationships with students. All students bring to the classroom experiences, strengths, and weaknesses that make them unique individuals. Nevertheless, among a diverse classroom of unique students is a single teacher with the responsibility to educate. As has previously noted, a key component of this education is the establishment of high quality, positive interpersonal relationships with students.

XIV. Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Teacher's Performance

The profession of teaching requires the ability to handle stressful circumstances of dealing with work pressure as well as maintenance of decorum within the classroom. According to Pitchers (1995) hinted at a possibility of burnout out experienced by teachers due to the high level of stress that they are exposed to on a day-to-day basis (p.78). To deal with the high job stress and the risk of burnout, the instructors need to be equipped with the ability to effectively manage their and the student's emotional states. Neale (2006) has asserted that one of the basic reasons why an emotionally intelligent leader and coaches can perform well is that they are not only able to identify their areas of strength, but are also capable of actively seeking strengths in other individuals. Teacher in a similar manner can facilitate the educational development of children through observing their strengths and using them as a means of gaining leverage against the limitations of the students. Moreover, it is also, imperative to note that emotionally intelligent teachers can perform well in the classroom because they are an accurate judgment about the emotional state of the students.

XV. Part Two

This study has uses mixed methods to evaluate the value of objective and subjective knowledge. The research design explored the research questions of this pilot study required the use of the questionnaire and interview method were used to collect the data. The calculation and interpretation of means, ranges and standard deviations, across individuals and groups of teachers and students.

XVI. 2.1 Participants

For this study, 65 students were optionally selected from 2 universities in Kurdistan Region Iraq for a questionnaire from schools/ colleges/ universities in the Kurdistan Region Iraq. 21 teachers had participated in the interview from 2 universities in Iraqi Kurdistan Region.

XVII. 2.2 The account of research methodology and methods

According to Creswell (2007), a methodology is “the nature in which their research emerges” (p.238). In terms of a methodology, it seeks to answer the main research questions of how researchers will find out the results. Through this paradigm, the personal conflict of both qualitative or quantitative lines of inquiry will be prominent and the decision needs to be prudently considered. As stated by Comte (2000, p.55) that to build an actionable knowledge base; three research approaches must be considered; qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods.

XVIII. 2.3 Three Approaches to Research

In this study the three research approaches are advanced: qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods. Unquestionably, the three approaches are not discrete as they first appear.

XIX. 2.3.1 Qualitative Research

According to LeCompte & Schensul, (1999), qualitative data may be collected by observing participants or sites of research, gathering documents from a private or public source. The analysis of the qualitative data typically follows the path of aggregating the words or images into categories of information. The sources of the data do not effectively map onto qualitative and quantitative research, a least as much as they used to.

XX. 2.3.2 Quantitative Research

It is an approach for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. As stated by Thomas (2009), that “quantitative data includes closed-ended information such as that found on attitude behaviour or performance instruments” (p.19). The collection of this kind of data might also involve using a checklist, on which researchers’ checks the behaviour seen such as census records or attendance records.

XXI. 2.3.3 Mixed Methods Research

The researcher of this study has considered the mixed methods, the core assumption of this form of inquiry is that the combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches provides a complete understanding of a research problem than either approach alone. According to Raz and Zysberg (2014), it is an approach to the inquiry involving collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, integrating the two forms of data and using distinct designs that involve philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks (p.45).

XXII. 2.4 Choice of Methods

The choice of methods will be influenced by ontological and epistemological assumptions. In the minds of many researchers, certain methods are inextricably bound up with certain ontological and epistemological assumptions: for example, try asking an enthusiastic rational choice theorist what she thinks of discourse analysis. The significant thing to note here is that it is the researcher who employs a particular method in a particular way, thereby associating it with a specific set of ontological assumptions. Unquestionably, the three approaches are not as discrete as they first appear. Qualitative and quantitative approaches should not be viewed as rigid, distinct categories, opposites, or dichotomies. Lastly, in this study, the researcher used mixed methods as an approach to the inquiry involving collecting both qualitative and quantitative data. According to Creswell (2007), those methods are the tools and techniques that are used in the collection and analysis of data. The philosophical background of research can determine the types of methods that are appropriate. Once the most appropriate methodology has been identified, there are likely to be methods specific to the methodology.

XXIII. 2.5 Methods of Data Collection

To practically answer the main research questions of this study, and further prove the importance of research methods in the educational sector in Kurdistan Region Iraq. To investigate this matter, an experimental study was conducted with the participation of 65 students from 2 universities in the Iraqi Kurdistan Region and 21 teachers were interviewed from 3 schools within 2 universities. The following table in (table 1), shows the teacher demographics. Thus, eleven teachers in this study-maintained rank one status. Teachers earn rank one status which is awarded to lecturers with a PhD degree. Ten teachers held rank two status which is awarded assistant lecturers with a Master’s degree.

Teachers	Gender	Age	Education Rank	Years of Experience
Teacher A	Male	34	2	10
Teacher B	Male	45	1	15
Teacher C	Male	41	1	13
Teacher D	Female	39	1	14
Teacher E	Female	29	2	8
Teacher F	Male	38	1	10
Teacher H	Male	36	2	11
Teacher G	Female	27	2	7
Teacher I	Male	27	2	10

(Table 1. Teacher Demographics)

**XXIV. Part Three
The findings and Discussions**

This part presents the primary purpose of this mixed-methods study to investigate the relationship between teachers’ emotional intelligence, interpersonal relationship quality, and student engagement and achievement. This study utilized semi-structured interviews with teachers, teacher emotional intelligence scores, and teacher-student relationship quality questionnaire data. For the interviews, there were 9 female and 12 male participants in the study. For the questionnaire, there were 65 students (25female and 40male) optionally selected. During this study, the following three main research questions were used to guide the investigation.

- 1) What are the challenges of the teacher emotional intelligence related to student achievement?
- 2) What are the most significant impacts on teachers to use emotional intelligence to establish interpersonal relationships with students?
- 3) To what extent does emotional intelligence impact student engagement?

Research question 1: What are the challenges of the teacher emotional intelligence related to student achievement? The findings of research question one was very interesting that shows the challenges of teacher emotional intelligence related to student’s achievement. Table (1) has shown the four main challenges in which 20 out of 21 candidates’ interviews were mentioned correspondingly.

The four main challenges of teacher emotional intelligence	Total (n=21)
Managing Emotions: Self-confidence	20
Understanding emotions in Teaching	19
Facilitating Thought: Create a Mindset	18
Perceiving Emotions: Professional Relationship	20

(Table 2. The Four Main Challenges of Teacher Emotional Intelligence)

The above table is regarding the first research question that the main four challenges of teacher emotional intelligence were identified. **First**, the majority (20 out of 21) of teachers’ respondents have the managing emotions in self-confidence. Thus, emotions often can be managed. To the extent that it is under self-control, a person may want to remain open to emotional signals so long as they are not too painful, and block out those that are irresistible. Additionally, within the person’s emotional comfort zone, it becomes and manages one’s own and others emotions to promote one’s own and others’ personal and social goals. An emotionally intelligent teacher can guide students in a better way. The **second** challenge is understanding emotions in teaching. Most of the respondents’ (19 out of 21), have mentioned that understating emotions is vital in teaching. Emotions convey their pattern of possible messages in the classroom and actions associated with those messages. This united with the capacity to reason about those meanings. For instance, poor participation by the student in a particular subject means the students feel alien to the group or course in the classroom. The **third** challenge (18 out of 21) teachers were mentioned is how to use emotions to facilitate thoughts. This was the

capacity of the emotions to guide the cognitive system and promote thinking and help direct thinking toward truly vital matters. Several researchers have suggested that emotions are important for a certain kind of creativity to emerge. For example: if one doesn't understand the hunger of another, he cannot get the thought of helping the poor, if the teacher fails to understand the weakness of student, then he cannot evolve ways to overcome the student's problem. A 13 mentioned that "it is difficult to imagine effective teachers who not have an abiding facilitating thought, who does not love being among students, and who do not gain fulfilment from nourishing others' minds and lives". Questionably, A 26 pointed out a similar problem to A 13.

The **fourth** challenge is perceiving emotions (20 out of 21) participants were identified. This is the nonverbal reception and facial expressions such as happiness, sadness, anger, and fear that were universally recognizable in human beings. The capacity to accurately perceive emotions in the face or voice of others provides a crucial starting point for a more advanced understanding of emotions. For example: seeing a student's face we ask 'what happen' hearing once the voice over the phone we ask 'are you alright. A 17 has stated "a positive mindset can give me more confidence, improve my mood, and even reduce the likelihood of developing conditions such as hypertension, depression and other stress-related disorders that cannot start the day with a positive affirmation.

(Graphic 1. The Four Main Challenges of Teacher Emotional Intelligence)

Research question 2: What are the most significant impacts on teachers to use emotional intelligence to establish interpersonal relationships with students?

Collecting two forms of data was central to investigating the emotional intelligence (EI) of teachers that influenced teacher-student relationship quality, and student achievement and engagement. Quantitative data were collected using the online- questionnaire of emotional understanding to determine teachers (EI) score. Thus, the findings of research question two show that there are five significant impacts on teachers to use emotional intelligence to establish interpersonal relationships with students. From Graphic 2, it becomes clear and concise that five main significant factors impact teacher performance relationship with students.

(Graphic 2. The Five Main Factors impact on Teacher Emotional Intelligence)

Inside graphic 2, it has shown that five factors impact teacher emotional intelligence to launch a good relationship with students. First, (30%) the majority of teachers' respondents' have mentioned stress is the impact on teacher emotional intelligence. For example, handling anger is the reaction to an event, the reason for anger may be small or big, none away from this emotion. It can be handled by identifying the reason which caused anger. A13 stated that "the span of anger differs from person to person; the emotionally intelligent person will not keep anger for long. It is considered a healthy emotion when it is expressed appropriately. The second factor is inter-personal, which is the negative emotions inside a person will reflect on his face, and unpleasing facial gesture of teacher may scare or discourage student to learn a particular subject. 25% of teachers have mentioned is anxiety affects their emotions in the classroom. A11 pointed out that "stress is influence teachers on emotional intelligence, for example; escape from one problem is not the problem solution, instead of reacting naturally and try to find the root cause of that problem.

The third factor is the adaptability that the results of coding teacher interviews revealed that of the 21 participating teachers, 17 (14%) reported having flexibility with students leads to high academic achievement and impact on teacher emotional intelligence to establish a good relationship. The fourth factor is self-motivation, which (14%) of teachers believe if the person controls his or her emotions carefully rather than just reacting to a situation solely based on impulse generated by an emotion-generating event. A16 has mentioned this "the person exhibit interest and an ability in recognizing the feelings of others. Empathy gives on the ability to "walk in the other person's shoes". Finally, the fifth factor is the general mood that is the second-highest coding from the results (25%) have mentioned. For instance, A 19 has stated that the negative emotions inside a person will reflect on his face, her/his general mood, and unpleasing facial gesture of teacher may scare or discourage student to learn a particular subject.

Research question 3: To what extent does emotional intelligence impact student engagement?

The findings of research question three was compound because two forms data were central to be completed. The first form, 19 out of 21 candidates' interviews were mentioned correspondingly. The second form, the questionnaire, which there were 65 students (25female and 40male) optionally selected. Table (3) has shown the four main influences that extent the emotional intelligence impact students' performance.

The four main influences that impact student's performance	Total (n=21)	Total (n=65)
Student Engagement	20	61
Emotional Engagement	19	58
Behavioural Engagement	18	53
Cognitive Engagement	20	48

(Table 3. The Four Main Influences that Impact student's performance)

According to the literature review on this study, the relationship quality encompasses two components from the perspective of the student: 1) level of support from the teacher and 2) level of conflict with the teacher (Hughes, 2012, p.88). Hence, this is very good confirmation from the findings. From table (3) and graphic have shown that four main influences power students' performance.

1. Student Engagement

The theoretical link between teacher EI and student engagement and achievement does exist. Thus, this study has found that teachers who possess high levels of EI should be able to influence the emotional and behavioural engagement of students. This influence should then also lead to cognitive engagement and eventually to increases in student academic achievement. Conversely, the engagement of students is not static, having been shown to be fluid over time with the great variance within individual students over the academic achievement. According to Fredricks, & Paris (2004), they pointed out that student engagement is currently viewed as a meta-construct emotional, and cognitive engagement was the first to propose this meta-construct recognizing that engagement within the literature often used separate and unique descriptions of the concept. Generally, the engagement of all students decreases as they progress through the educational system.

(Graphic 3. The Four Main Influences that Impact student's performance)

2. Emotional Engagement

The theoretical link between teacher EI and student engagement and achievement does exist. Thus, this study has found that teachers who possess high levels of EI should be able to influence the emotional and behavioral engagement of students. This influence should then also lead to cognitive engagement and eventually to increases in student academic achievement. It shows in table 3 that most of the teachers have mentioned (20 out of 21) as the main influences that extent the emotional intelligence impact students' performance. Additionally, (61 out of 65) students have motioned that the feelings associated with emotional engagement can be influenced by social dimensions, including peers and teachers. Furthermore, student emotional engagement is

defined as student affective response to learning activities and the people associated with those activities (Park, 2012).

3. Behavioural Engagement

Prior evidence provided in this study has demonstrated that teaching and learning are emotional endeavours see table 3. The ability of teachers' intelligence to influence the engagement of students through quality, interpersonal relationships is significant. According to Fredricks, 2004, p.37), students' behavioural engagement is defined as participation and involvement in academic and social activities. behavioural is the observable act of students being involved in learning; it refers to students' participation in academic activities and efforts to perform academic tasks. Put simply students who are behaviorally engaged are active participants in the learning and social activities of the college or university. It would stand to reason that those students who are more involved, both socially and academically, achieve more than those who are not.

4. Cognitive Engagement

The evidence provided in this study has demonstrated that a challenge for professional developers charged with training teachers for student success, then, is to help teachers align their instruction with principles and practices for cognitive engagement. Conversely, student cognitive engagement has been defined by Fredricks (2004, p.45), as an investment in learning on the part of the student. Furthermore, cognitive engagement was further elucidated by Watt, Carmichael, and Callingham (2017, p.78) who stated that it is an epistemic curiosity that serves as motivation. The cognitively engaged student displays a thoughtful approach toward learning and a willingness to put forth the necessary effort to comprehend complex ideas. Untimely, this study has explained students' cognitive engagement involves the students to think during the academic task, they have to have motivated to improve their ability in learning and also, they have to participate and act in the classroom.

XXV. Conclusion

The study of teacher emotional intelligence is very new. In conclusion, the researcher briefly discussed the main aim of the relationship between teacher intelligence, teacher-student relationship quality, and student engagement. It shows the significance of critical relationship quality with students. Appreciatively, a statistically significant relationship between teacher emotional intelligence and the teacher-student relationship was found. This study has well succeeded as the similar points stated by Mehta (2015, p.67), the educational landscape has been dominated by an emphasis on reform efforts focused on standards-based curriculum and standardized achievement measurement. Furthermore, teacher evaluation processes are changing nationwide. Educators have come to a place in time when research must answer questions about the specific attributes of successful teachers and how those attributes correlate with student outcomes. Additionally, the study is recommended. Emotional intelligence, as a construct, has the promise to provide a meaningful answer about the successful working relationships between teachers and students in a classroom. Finally, the findings show in this study that several implications have been found. The first is that the teacher may impact beliefs about the ability of the student to achieve academically. The second is may influence teachers' ability to impact student engagement. The third implication of this study is that teachers view the functions of interpersonal relationships within the classroom in a variety of ways. Ultimately, emotional intelligence plays a fundamental role in teaching training and while it must include in academic training, it is also necessary for a social and emotional context. This study has found that the more emotionally skilled a prospective teacher is, the greater control he/she has with the school context.

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